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Underwater Security

UnderSec Consortium is a multidisciplinary group composed of 22 partners from 11 different countries

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Protecting ships and maritime infrastructures against illegal acts

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The project in brief

Ships, maritime infrastructures and the whole marine ecosystem need to be sufficiently protected against possible illegal acts, by also fostering underwater security and assuring secure navigation. UnderSec is dedicated to enhancing maritime and underwater security. The project involves a consortium of experts, research institutions, and technology partners, aiming to develop a comprehensive underwater security solution.

The objective

UnderSec aims to develop a comprehensive underwater security system for maritime assets and infrastructures using multimodal sensors and robotic assets.

The Pilots

UnderSec relies on four Real-life Pilot Use Cases (PUC) scenarios that will be the basis for the demonstration, testing and evaluation of all UnderSec system's capabilities and capacities.

The technical framework

The UnderSec system employs a layers-based approach, comprising "Horizontal" Layers of Protection Technologies and "Logical" Layers of Data Management and Exploitation. The former organizes components for specific underwater security tasks, while the latter ensures proper data management, governance, analysis, and exploitation.

